

DHA SUFFA UNIVERSITY

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR SUPPLY CHAIN OPTIMIZATION AND EFFICIENCY (ICISSC) – 2025

August 7–8, 2025

Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability
in Global Supply Chains

Conference Proceedings

Organized by:

**Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center (BSRIC)
and Professional Development Center (PDC)**

in collaboration with

**Department of Management Sciences, Faculty of Management Sciences,
DHA Suffa University, Karachi**

**DHA Suffa University
Phase VII (Extension), DHA Karachi**

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**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INNOVATIVE
STRATEGIES FOR SUPPLY CHAIN OPTIMIZATION AND
EFFICIENCY (ICISSC) – 2025**

August 7–8, 2025

**Theme: Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global
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Conference Proceedings

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PREFACE

It is with great pleasure that we present the proceedings of the International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025, held on August 7–8, 2025, at DHA Suffa University, Karachi. This two-day event brought together a vibrant mix of scholars, practitioners, policymakers, and students to explore strategies that enhance agility, resilience, and sustainability in global supply chains.

The theme—Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global Supply Chains—was both timely and critical, especially in a post-pandemic world facing unprecedented disruptions and technological advancements. Over 40 research papers and posters were selected through a rigorous peer-review process. These contributions span diverse topics, including digital transformation, sustainable procurement, AI integration, behavioral supply chain management, and logistics optimization.

The conference was organized by the Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center (BSRIC) and the Department of Management Sciences, in collaboration with the Professional Development Center (PDC) at DHA Suffa University. We extend our gratitude to all keynote speakers, session chairs, reviewers, and contributors who played an essential role in shaping the academic and professional discourse.

These proceedings reflect the high quality of research and the innovative ideas presented during the conference. We hope that the papers compiled here will serve as a valuable resource for researchers, industry professionals, and policy advisors aiming to develop adaptive and intelligent supply chain solutions.

We also thank Vice-Chancellor Brig (R) Prof. Dr. Ahmed Saeed Minhas, DHA Suffa University, for his continued commitment to promoting research excellence and interdisciplinary collaboration. We look forward to future editions of ICISSC and the continued exchange of impactful knowledge.

Dr. Ammad Zafar

Conference Chair, ICISSC 2025
Head, Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center
Associate Professor, Department of Management Sciences
DHA Suffa University, Karachi

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MESSAGE FROM PATRON

It gives me great pleasure to extend my heartfelt congratulations on the successful organization of the *International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025*, hosted by DHA Suffa University. As Patron of this prestigious event, I am proud to see our institution playing a pivotal role in bringing together leading scholars, practitioners, industry experts, and policymakers to explore transformative strategies for the future of global supply chains.

In today's interconnected and rapidly evolving world, supply chain systems face increasing complexity due to technological disruptions, sustainability challenges, and economic uncertainties. The need for innovative, agile, and data-driven solutions is more urgent than ever. ICISSC 2025 addresses these challenges head-on by offering a platform for rigorous academic discourse, practical insight, and collaborative exploration.

DHA Suffa University has always been committed to fostering a culture of research excellence, critical thinking, and interdisciplinary engagement. This conference reflects those values and reinforces our mission to be a hub of innovation and thought leadership in Pakistan and the region.

I commend the efforts of the organizing team, the Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center (BSRIC), the Professional Development Center (PDC), and the Department of Management Sciences for their dedication and vision. I also extend my appreciation to the keynote speakers, authors, reviewers, and participants who have contributed to the success of this event.

May the outcomes of ICISSC 2025 inspire meaningful change in both academic inquiry and industry practice, and may DHA Suffa University continue to serve as a beacon for impactful learning and research.

Brig (R) Prof. Dr. Ahmed Saeed Minhas
Vice-Chancellor
DHA Suffa University

MESSAGE FROM HEAD OF BUSINESS SOLUTIONS, RESEARCH, AND INNOVATION CENTER

It gives me immense pride and satisfaction to welcome you to the *International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025*, hosted at DHA Suffa University. Organized under the joint collaboration of the Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center (BSRIC), the Professional Development Center (PDC), and the Department of Management Sciences, this conference represents our shared commitment to advancing knowledge, innovation, and practical solutions in the evolving field of supply chain management.

At BSRIC, our mission is to bridge the gap between academia and industry by promoting applied research, data-driven insights, and real-world impact. ICISSC 2025 is a reflection of that vision—bringing together thought leaders, scholars, and practitioners from diverse sectors to engage in meaningful discourse on strategic supply chain transformation.

The growing complexities of global trade, digital disruption, sustainability imperatives, and geopolitical uncertainty have elevated the importance of resilient, agile, and technology-enabled supply chains. This conference, through its diverse themes and research contributions, offers a critical lens into the tools, strategies, and mindsets required to navigate these challenges.

I want to express my heartfelt gratitude to our keynote speakers, session chairs, reviewers, participants, and the entire organizing team for their valuable contributions and dedication. I am particularly thankful to our young researchers and students, whose enthusiasm and innovative thinking continue to inspire the future of business and logistics.

I hope that the insights shared during this conference will inspire new research, spark strategic collaborations, and lead to sustainable advancements in the global supply chain landscape.

Dr. Ammad Zafar

Conference Chair, ICISSC 2025
Head, Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center
Associate Professor, Department of Management Sciences
DHA Suffa University, Karachi

MESSAGE FROM DIRECTOR, PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT CENTER (PDC)

It is a privilege to extend my warmest congratulations on the successful execution of the *International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025*, hosted at DHA Suffa University. As the Director of the Professional Development Center (PDC), I am delighted to witness how this conference has created a collaborative platform where academia meets industry, and innovation intersects with practice.

PDC has always aimed to support initiatives that enhance lifelong learning, professional excellence, and knowledge exchange. ICISSC 2025 embodies these values by bringing together researchers, practitioners, policymakers, and students to explore the critical themes shaping modern supply chains—agility, sustainability, resilience, and digital transformation.

This conference is not merely an academic gathering; it is a dynamic environment for practical insight, cross-disciplinary dialogue, and the co-creation of knowledge that addresses real-world challenges. The diversity of topics, depth of analysis, and engagement of young researchers reflect the vibrant intellectual energy we strive to cultivate at DHA Suffa University.

I am particularly proud of the role PDC has played in facilitating executive learning sessions, workshops, and panel discussions that enhance both academic and professional capabilities. These engagements contribute significantly to shaping the future of business, logistics, and operational excellence in Pakistan and beyond.

I extend my sincere thanks to all speakers, authors, reviewers, and attendees whose contributions have enriched this conference. A special note of appreciation goes to the organizing team for their tireless commitment and attention to detail.

May ICISSC continue to grow as a flagship platform for research and innovation, and may the ideas shared here spark meaningful change in supply chain systems around the world.

Dr. Shahid Raza Mir

Director, Professional Development Center (PDC)
DHA Suffa University, Karachi

MESSAGE FROM DEAN, FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCE

It is with immense pride and pleasure that I extend my warmest regards on the occasion of the *International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025*, organized by DHA Suffa University. As the Dean of the Faculty of Management Sciences, I am delighted to witness this platform evolve into a hub of intellectual exchange, academic rigor, and industry-academia collaboration.

The theme of this year’s conference—*Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global Supply Chains*—addresses some of the most pressing challenges in contemporary business environments. In an era defined by disruption and transformation, supply chain innovation is critical for organizational survival and long-term growth. This conference provides a timely and strategic opportunity to explore such innovation through research, dialogue, and shared experiences.

I am particularly proud of the contributions made by our faculty members, researchers, and students in ensuring the success of ICISSC 2025. Their enthusiasm, commitment, and academic excellence are reflected in the diverse range of papers presented and the thought-provoking discussions held throughout the sessions.

I would like to commend the organizing bodies—Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center (BSRIC), the Professional Development Center (PDC), and the Department of Management Sciences—for their outstanding efforts in hosting this event. I also express my appreciation to our distinguished speakers, reviewers, session chairs, and all participants for enriching the conference with their insights.

I hope that the ideas generated here will inspire future research and drive meaningful improvements in the practice of supply chain management—locally and globally.

Prof. Dr. Imtiaz Arif
Dean, Faculty of Management Sciences
DHA Suffa University, Karachi

MESSAGE FROM HEAD OF DEPARTMENT, MANAGEMENT SCIENCES

It is a matter of great honor and pride for the Department of Management Sciences to be a key organizing partner of the *International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025*, hosted at DHA Suffa University. This conference marks a significant milestone in our ongoing efforts to promote high-impact research, foster academic–industry collaboration, and contribute meaningfully to the global discourse on supply chain transformation.

In an era defined by rapid digitalization, shifting consumer expectations, and increasing environmental concerns, the role of supply chain management has never been more critical. ICISSC 2025 provides a timely platform to explore innovative solutions and strategic responses to the complex challenges faced by today’s supply chains.

As Head of the Department of Management Sciences, I take immense pride in the active participation of our faculty, students, and research scholars in this initiative. Their contributions—ranging from academic papers to organizational support—have helped shape this conference into a space of meaningful dialogue and knowledge exchange. The diverse range of topics covered, including sustainability, digital technologies, procurement practices, and behavioral insights, reflects our department’s multidisciplinary strength and commitment to relevance and excellence.

I extend my heartfelt appreciation to all contributors, including our esteemed keynote speakers, paper presenters, and reviewers, for their dedication and thought leadership. I am especially grateful to the organizing team whose tireless efforts made this event a success.

I am confident that the ideas shared and networks formed during this conference will lead to long-lasting collaborations, impactful research, and transformative practices in supply chain management.

Dr. Sobia Iqbal

Head of Department, Management Sciences
Associate Professor, DHA Suffa University, Karachi

MESSAGE FROM THE GUEST OF HONOUR MEMBER, SINDH HEC

GOVERNMENT OF SINDH
SINDH HIGHER EDUCATION COMMISSION
CHARTER INSPECTION & EVALUATION COMMITTEE
F-60, Near Abdullah Shah Ghazi Shrine, Shahrah-e-Attar,
Clifton, Block-4 Karachi, Ph: 021-99332669-71
info@sindhhec.gov.pk, www.sindhhec.gov.pk

No. DG/CIEC-SHEC/ 442 /2025

Dated: 11 /08 /2025

To,
The Vice Chancellor,
DHA Suffa University,
Karachi.

Subject: GREETINGS AND BEST WISHES FOR INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE ON INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR SUPPLY CHAIN
OPTIMIZATION AND EFFICIENCY (ICISSC) – 2025

I am delighted to extend my warmest greetings and best wishes to all participants, speakers, and organizers International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025.

This conference is a timely and important initiative that may bring together the academia, industries, and policymakers to address the challenges and opportunities in modern supply chain management. This shall focus on innovation, sustainability, and the integration of emerging technologies such as AI reflects a forward-looking vision that aligns with the global direction of higher education and industry collaboration.

I commend DHA Suffa University, its faculty, and partners for creating this platform for knowledge sharing and solution driven dialogue. I am confident that the outcomes of ICISSC 2025 will contribute meaningfully to Pakistan's academic excellence, industrial competitiveness, and economic development.

For:

Dr. Noman Ahsan
Director General (Coordination and CIEC),
Sindh Higher Education Commission

Copy forwarded for information to:

1. P.S to the Chairperson, Sindh HEC, Government of Sindh, Karachi.
2. P.S to the Secretary, Sindh HEC, Government of Sindh, Karachi
3. Concerned File/ Folder.

MESSAGE FROM THE GUEST OF HONOUR

It was an absolute honour to attend the **International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025** at DHA Suffa University as Guest of Honour.

The conference successfully brought together distinguished scholars, industry experts, and policymakers to share valuable insights, research, and best practices in the evolving field of supply chain management. The diversity of topics—from sustainable logistics to AI-driven optimization—demonstrated the organizers’ commitment to addressing both present and future challenges in the sector.

I was deeply impressed by the dedication of the organizing team, the enthusiasm of the participants, and the quality of discussions that took place. Such collaborative platforms are vital for bridging the gap between academia and industry, fostering innovation, and equipping the next generation of professionals with the skills and vision needed for global competitiveness.

I congratulate DHA Suffa University, the Department of Management Sciences, and their partners for hosting such a meaningful and impactful event. I look forward to seeing the continued growth and success of this initiative in the years to come.

Prof. Dr. Saima Akhtar
Chairperson
Department of Public Administration
University of Karachi

MESSAGE FROM THE DISTINGUISHED GUEST

It was a privilege to be part of the **International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025** at DHA Suffa University.

This conference provided an exceptional platform for meaningful dialogue between academia and industry, addressing the pressing challenges and emerging opportunities in the global supply chain landscape. The focus on innovation, digital transformation, and sustainability resonates strongly with the evolving needs of businesses and the economy at large.

I was encouraged to see students, researchers, and professionals actively engaging in discussions, sharing ideas, and presenting solutions that can make a tangible difference. Such initiatives are essential for nurturing talent, fostering partnerships, and driving Pakistan's competitiveness in global markets.

I commend the organizers, speakers, and participants for their dedication in making ICISSC 2025 a resounding success and look forward to seeing the outcomes of this collaboration put into practice.

Mr. Tauqir Khokhar
Chief Executive Officer
CK International

CK INTERNATIONAL

We are proud to have **CK International** as one of our valued sponsors for the *International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025*.

Founded in 2005, CK International is among Pakistan’s fastest-growing professional services firms, with offices in Karachi and Gujranwala. Built on the core values of **integrity, commitment, and excellence**, CK International offers strategic, value-driven solutions in **audit, accounting, taxation, customs, and consultancy** tailored to client-specific needs.

Specializing in **tax management, customs compliance, and accounting support**, CK International also provides expert services in **import/export clearances, supply chain compliance, and trade facilitation**. Operating under the principles of quality and client trust, the firm helps businesses optimize processes, reduce costs, and ensure compliance with complex regulatory frameworks.

CK International is committed to building long-term partnerships, empowering clients to achieve their goals through professionalism, personalized service, and innovative solutions. Their dedication to excellence and customer satisfaction continues to set them apart as a trusted leader in the professional services sector.

We thank CK International for their generous support and partnership in making ICISSC 2025 a success.

EDITORIAL

The *International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025*, held at DHA Suffa University, arrives at a pivotal moment when global supply chains are undergoing intense transformation driven by digitization, sustainability imperatives, and resilience challenges. This editorial introduces a curated collection of research papers, case studies, and conceptual frameworks that reflect emerging thinking and evidence-based practices in the field of supply chain management.

The conference theme—*Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global Supply Chains*—captures the multifaceted nature of contemporary logistics and procurement systems. The papers in this volume span diverse and timely areas including AI integration in logistics, sustainable procurement strategies, behavioral dynamics in supply chain decision-making, and data-driven approaches to inventory and demand management. Notably, several studies contextualize these global issues within the realities of developing economies, offering a grounded yet forward-looking perspective.

As editors, we are pleased to observe the growing engagement of young scholars and early-career professionals, whose work is both academically rigorous and practically relevant. The quality of submissions and the range of methodological approaches—from quantitative modeling to mixed-method investigations—demonstrate the maturity and evolution of supply chain research in Pakistan and the broader region.

This proceeding is not just a record of conference contributions; it is a resource for continued dialogue among academia, industry, and policy circles. We encourage readers to explore these papers with a critical eye and open mind, as each presents an opportunity to refine strategy, improve systems, and inspire innovation.

We extend our sincere appreciation to the reviewers, session chairs, and contributors who made this volume possible. We hope that these proceedings will inform practice, influence policy, and fuel future research in global supply chain excellence.

Editorial Board

ICISSC 2025 – DHA Suffa University

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR SUPPLY CHAIN OPTIMIZATION AND EFFICIENCY (ICISSC) -2025

August 7-8, 2025

Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global Supply Chains

2-Day International Conference Organized by: Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center and Department of Management Sciences, in collaboration with the Professional Development Center (PDC), DHA Suffa University

CONFERENCE OVERVIEW

In the rapidly evolving global economic landscape, supply chains face increased pressures from geopolitical risks, technological advancements, sustainability demands and shifting consumer behavior. The **International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency** aims to bring together international scholars, practitioners, policymakers, and industry experts to share, explore, and advance cutting-edge strategies that drive operational excellence, resilience, and sustainability in supply chain systems.

This conference offers a dynamic platform for interdisciplinary collaboration across operations management, logistics, technology, analytics, sustainability, procurement, and policy domains. It will highlight best practices and explore research-based, data-driven strategies to transform supply chains into agile, transparent, and resilient value networks.

CONFERENCE OBJECTIVES

1. Explore Innovative Supply Chain Strategies

Showcase innovative frameworks, models, and tools that improve supply chain performance and agility across industries.

2. Foster Industry-Academia Collaboration

Promote collaboration between scholars and practitioners to bridge the gap between theory and practice in logistics, procurement, and supply chain analytics.

3. Encourage Sustainable Supply Chains

Present and discuss strategies for greener, more ethical, and circular supply chains aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

4. Highlight Digital Transformation

Explore the role of Industry 4.0, AI, IoT, blockchain, and big data analytics in modernizing supply chain operations.

5. Support Policy and Practice Development

Provide evidence-based insights to inform decision-makers on national and international supply chain policy and regulation.

6. Empower Emerging Scholars and Entrepreneurs

Offer a platform for students, researchers, and startups to present innovative ideas and engage with thought leaders.

CONFERENCE OBJECTIVES AND SDGS**Table 01: ICISSC 2025 to SDGs Mapping**

Conference Objective	Description	Relevant UN SDGs
1. Explore Innovative Supply Chain Strategies	Showcase innovative frameworks, models, and tools that improve supply chain performance and agility across industries.	SDG 8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth SDG 9 – Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure
2. Foster Industry-Academia Collaboration	Promote collaboration between scholars and practitioners to bridge the gap between theory and practice in logistics, procurement, and supply chain analytics.	SDG 4 – Quality Education SDG 17 – Partnerships for the Goals
3. Encourage Sustainable Supply Chains	Present and discuss strategies for greener, more ethical, and circular supply chains aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).	SDG 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production SDG 13 – Climate Action SDG 15 – Life on Land
4. Highlight Digital Transformation	Explore the role of Industry 4.0, AI, IoT, blockchain, and big data analytics in modernizing supply chain operations.	SDG 9 – Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure SDG 11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities
5. Support Policy and Practice Development	Provide evidence-based insights to inform decision-makers on national and international supply chain policy and regulation.	SDG 16 – Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions SDG 8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth
6. Empower Emerging Scholars and Entrepreneurs	Offer a platform for students, researchers, and startups to present innovative ideas and engage with thought leaders.	SDG 4 – Quality Education SDG 8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth SDG 17 – Partnerships for the Goals

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGS)

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a global blueprint for achieving a better and more sustainable future by 2030. Adopted by all UN Member States in 2015, the 17 goals address pressing challenges such as poverty, inequality, climate change, environmental degradation, peace, and justice. They serve as an urgent call to action for governments, businesses, academia, and civil society to work together in building a more inclusive, resilient, and sustainable world.

SDGs Addressed in ICISSC 2025

The **International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency** directly supports several SDGs through its themes, discussions, and collaborations:

- **SDG 4 – Quality Education:** Enhancing academic learning, research, and knowledge exchange between academia and industry.
- **SDG 8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth:** Promoting efficient, competitive, and innovative supply chain systems that generate economic opportunities.
- **SDG 9 – Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure:** Advancing modern, technology-driven supply chain models and infrastructure.
- **SDG 11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities:** Integrating sustainable logistics and smart urban delivery systems.
- **SDG 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production:** Encouraging greener and more ethical supply chain practices.
- **SDG 13 – Climate Action:** Addressing environmental impact through eco-friendly supply chain solutions.
- **SDG 15 – Life on Land:** Promoting sustainable sourcing and responsible use of natural resources.
- **SDG 16 – Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions:** Supporting evidence-based policymaking for transparent and resilient supply chain governance.
- **SDG 17 – Partnerships for the Goals:** Strengthening collaborations between academia, industry, and policymakers to achieve shared development objectives.

CONFERENCE THEMES

Main Theme: **Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency**

Sub-Themes Include (but are not limited to):

- Sustainable Supply Chain Practices
- Supply Chain Risk Management and Resilience
- Digital Supply Chain Transformation (AI, Blockchain, IoT)
- Logistics and Transportation Optimization
- Procurement and Vendor Management
- Circular and Green Supply Chains
- Supply Chain Transparency and Ethics
- Cold Chain and Healthcare Supply Chain Innovations
- E-Commerce and Last-Mile Delivery
- Supply Chain Performance Metrics and KPIs
- Smart Warehousing and Inventory Management
- Public-Private Partnerships in Logistics

Submission Guidelines

- **Abstracts:** 150–200 words, clearly stating the research problem, methodology, and expected contributions.
- **Full Papers:** Max. 5,000 words in APA format. Must be original and unpublished.
- **Presentations:** Oral and poster presentation formats available.

CONFERENCE DATES & TIMELINE

S. No.	Activity	Date
1	Call for Abstracts	July 18, 2025
2	Abstract Submission Deadline	July 25, 2025
3	Notification of Acceptance	July 25, 2025
4	Full Paper Submission	July 30, 2025
5	Camera Ready Submission	July 30, 2025
6	Conference Dates	August 7, 2025
7	Journal Publication (Selected Papers)	December 2025

CONFERENCE BENEFITS

- Present to a global academic and professional audience
- Receive constructive peer feedback
- Networking with industry and academic leaders
- Explore publication opportunities
- Certificate of participation and presentation
- Opportunity for interdisciplinary collaboration

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

- **Patron:** Vice-Chancellor, DHA Suffa University
- **Conference Chairs:** Dr. Ammad Zafar, Dr. Shahid Raza Mir, Prof. Dr Imtiaz Arif, Dr Sobia Iqbal
- **Conference Co-Chairs:** Dr Syed Shoeb Ahmed, Dr Azam Anwar, Dr Kamran Khan, Dr Sajjad Ashraf, Director CSCR & Alumni, Muhammad Waqas
- **Organizing Partners:** Professional Development Center (PDC), DSU, Business Solutions, Research, and Innovations Center (BSRIC), Department of Management Sciences, DHA Suffa University.

EDITORIAL BOARD

Name	Affiliation (DSU)
Prof. Dr Imtiaz Arif	Dean, Faculty of Management Sciences
Dr Shahid Raza Mir	Director, Professional Development Center
Dr Ammad Zafar	Head of Business Solutions, Research and Innovations Center Associate Professor, Department of Management Sciences
Dr Sobia Iqbal	HOD, Associate Professor, Department of Management Sciences
Dr Syed Shoeb Ahmed	Associate Professor, Department of Management Sciences
Dr Azam Khan	Program Manager Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA) Department of Management Sciences
Dr Kamran Khan	Associate Professor, Department of Management Sciences,
Dr Muhammad Sajjad	Assistant Professor, Department of Management Sciences
Dr Subika Rizvi	Director CSCR & Alumni
Mr. Muhammad Waqas	Program Manager, Business Analytics and Programming BS (BAP), Department of Management Sciences

CONTACT INFORMATION

For queries and submissions:

ammad.zafar@dsu.edu.pk; www.dsu.edu.pk

Participation Fee

All participants (presenters and attendees) are required to pay a nominal participation fee.

- **Participation Fee:** Rs. 1,500/–

Note:

Payment details and procedures will be shared upon acceptance of the abstract or receipt of registration confirmation.

DHA SUFFA UNIVERSITY (DSU)

Established in **2012**, DHA Suffa University is a dynamic **private research university** sponsored by the Defence Housing Authority (DHA), offering high-quality education across Engineering, Computing & IT, Management Sciences, Humanities & Social Sciences, and more. DHA Suffa University Wikipedia.

Vision & Mission

- **Vision:** To become a globally recognized institution of higher education and research, which would extend the frontiers of knowledge and contribute significantly to nation-building
- **Mission:** To achieve higher standards in teaching, learning and research for becoming a world-renowned academic institution.

Academic Strengths

- Offers undergraduate, master's, and doctoral degrees, including cutting-edge programs like **Software Engineering, Data Science, Computational & Industrial Mathematics, Business Analytics & Programming, Economics & International Relations, and Psychology.**
- **Accredited by HEC**, recognized by **PEC**, and aligned with standards of **NCEAC** and **NBEAC** for computing, engineering, and business programs, respectively

Campus & Facilities

- Main campus located in **Phase VII (Extension) DHA Karachi, with a newer DCK (DHA City Karachi) campus operational since 2020, designed to serve as a major educational hub with hundreds of acres and extensive student capacity**
- **Equipped with modern classrooms**, advanced labs, libraries, seminar halls, auditorium, sports and recreational facilities, and dedicated career development services

Research, Innovation & Industry Linkages

DSU promotes impactful research through international collaborations, faculty development programs, student exchange opportunities, and partnerships with public and private sector organizations. The university emphasizes applied research, innovation, and entrepreneurship to address real-world challenges.

Research Journals

DHA Suffa University publishes the following academic journals:

- **Suffa University Journal of Business Management (SUJBM)** – A peer-reviewed, semi-annual journal (ISSN 3078-2562) focusing on research in business and management.
- **Suffa Journal of Interdisciplinary Psychology (SJIP)** – Dedicated to promoting research in psychology and related disciplines.

Research Output & Partnerships

- DSU has produced **360+ publications**, with around **58% open access**, and over **5,800 citations** recorded between 2008–2023.
- Displays active international collaborations, such as MoUs with institutions like CISSS and Bilkent University, supporting joint research, workshops, internships, and conferences

Core Values & Culture

- Anchored in values of **Faith, Character, Learning, Diversity, and Discovery**, DSU nurtures open-minded, ethical, and socially responsible graduates.

DHA Suffa University continues its commitment to producing thoughtful professionals, creative innovators, and conscientious citizens equipped to meet national and global challenges.

Faculties at DHA Suffa University (DSU)

DSU hosts a diverse range of academic disciplines under its key faculties, each committed to academic excellence, innovation, and industry relevance:

- **Faculty of Engineering and Applied Sciences**
- **Faculty of Computing and Information Technology**
- **Faculty of Management Sciences**
- **Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences**

These faculties offer comprehensive undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral programs designed to equip students with cutting-edge knowledge, research capabilities, and professional skills aligned with global standards.

Faculty of Management Sciences

The Faculty of Management Sciences at DHA Suffa University is dedicated to delivering high-quality education in business and management. Offering dynamic programs across undergraduate, postgraduate, and doctoral levels, the faculty emphasizes modern theory and practical application in areas such as finance, marketing, HRM, supply chain, business analytics, and accounting. With a faculty composed of experienced academics and industry professionals, it fosters research-driven teaching, experiential learning, and strong industry partnerships. The faculty's mission is to develop ethical, innovative, and future-ready business leaders who can thrive in a globalized world.

Department of Management Sciences

The **Department of Management Sciences** under the Faculty of Management Sciences is committed to shaping future business leaders and scholars. With a dynamic portfolio of undergraduate to doctoral programs, the department promotes innovation, analytical thinking, and social responsibility. It emphasizes experiential learning through case studies, research projects, and strong industry-academic partnerships.

Programs Offered

1. **Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA)**
2. **Bachelor of Science in Accounting and Finance (BS A&F)**
3. **Bachelor of Science in Business Analytics and Programming (BS BAP)**
4. **Master of Business Administration (MBA)**
5. **MS in Management Sciences**
6. **PhD in Management Sciences**

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT CENTER (PDC)

The **Professional Development Center (PDC)** at DHA Suffa University serves as the premier hub for lifelong learning and professional growth. Established with the vision to empower individuals across academia, industry, and government sectors, PDC offers innovative, high-impact training programs designed to enhance leadership, technical skills, and strategic acumen.

PDC's Executive Education portfolio includes workshops and short courses in general management, technology, marketing, and leadership—tailored to stay ahead of emerging business and innovation trends. Through seminars, speaker sessions, custom trainings, and certificate programs, PDC fosters academia–industry linkages and promotes mutual learning and discourse.

Over its history, PDC has delivered over **450 programs**, including **over 80 workshops and over 70 customized initiatives** annually. It has trained more than **100 executives** and supported graduate students with academic and professional skill development, empowering them to realize their full potential.

Connect with PDC to elevate your career, stay ahead of trends, and unlock new opportunities through continuous learning and strategic professional development.

BUSINESS SOLUTIONS, RESEARCH & INNOVATION CENTER (BSRIC)

The **Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center (BSRIC)** at DHA Suffa University is a dynamic platform dedicated to bridging the gap between academia, industry, and society through practical business solutions, applied research, and innovative thinking.

BSRIC aims to foster a culture of problem-solving, entrepreneurship, and industry-driven innovation. It facilitates collaborative research projects, consultancy services, and real-world case-based learning by engaging faculty, students, and external stakeholders. The center also supports startups, business incubations, and industry-academic linkages to address current market needs and drive sustainable growth.

Through seminars, conferences, workshops, and strategic partnerships, BSRIC plays a vital role in enhancing organizational performance, promoting research commercialization, and nurturing future business leaders equipped with creative and analytical capabilities.

BSRIC is committed to advancing knowledge, supporting evidence-based policymaking, and providing impactful solutions to real-world business challenges.

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR SUPPLY CHAIN OPTIMIZATION AND EFFICIENCY

Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global Supply Chains

Organized by the Department of Management Sciences, DHA Suffa University

Thursday, August 7, 2025

Time	Activities	Venue
09:00 AM - 09:30 AM	Registration	ELT
	Participants arrive and register.	ELT
Opening Sessions		
	Recitation of the Holy Quraan	ELT
	National Anthem	ELT
	Welcome address by Honorable Vice-Chancellor, DHA Suffa University: Brig. (R) Prof. Dr. Ahmed Saeed Minhas	ELT
	Conference Insight from Prof. Dr Imtiaz Arif	ELT
	Conference Background by Dr Shahid Raza Mir	ELT
	Conference theme and objectives by Dr Ammad Zafar	ELT
	Guest of Honor Dr Noman Ahsan, Director General (Coordination and CIEC) Sindh HEC	ELT
	Guest of Honor Prof. Dr Saima Akhtar, Chairperson, Department of Public Administration, University of Karachi.	ELT
Speaker Sessions		
10:15 AM - 11:30 AM	Keynote Speaker Mr. Adnan Ahmed, Former CEO of Avery Dennison Current Trends in Supply Chain Globally and in Pakistan	ELT
	International Keynote Speaker Dr Sharfuddin Khan, Associate Professor, University of Regina Digitalization and Supply Chain Management: Benefits, Challenges, and Opportunities	ELT
	International Keynote Speaker Prof. Dr Shujaat Mubarik, Heriot-Watt University, United Kingdom From Policy to Practice: Building Resilience in the age of disruptions	
	Guest Speaker: Mr. Raza Farooqui, General Secretary PIFFA Role of Freight Forwarder in Supply Chain Management and Key Challenges in Pakistan	ELT
	Guest Speaker: Mr. Khurram Hussain Hidayatallah, Director & Principal PIFFA Sustainability in the Supply Chain & Logistics sector	ELT
Souvenir & Certificate Distribution and Group Photograph		
11:30 AM - 11:45 AM	Tea Break	ELT

Time	Activities	Venue
Paper Presentation Parallel Sessions		
Research Paper Presentation Parallel Session 1 Session Chairs: Dr Salman Khatani Co-Session Chair: Muhammad Waqas		
11:45 AM - 12:45 PM	Fahad Akhtar, Faculty at PIFFA Challenges of the Supply Chain in Pakistan	ELT
	The Role of AI in Business Decision Making Novish Israfeel	ELT
	Optimizing Supply Chain Costs through Operational Integration: A Quantitative Analysis of Inventory and Warehouse Strategy Syed Hafeez ur Rehman	ELT
	The Impact of Blockchain Technology on Supply Chain Management: Evidence from the Textile Industry in Pakistan Javeria Khan	ELT
	Role of AI-Driven Practice on Supply Chain Management: A Study in Karachi Sabreen Iqbal	ELT
	The Effect of E-Commerce on Supply Chain Design Abdul Moeed	ELT
	Research Paper Presentation Parallel Session 2 Session Chairs: Dr Syed Shoeb Ahmed Co-Session Chair: Dr Asma Irfan	
11:45 AM - 12:45 PM	The Impact of Inventory Management on Customer Satisfaction in Karachi Najam Asif	CR 51A
	Adoption of SCM 4.0 In Pakistan: Investigating Perceived Benefits on Supply Chain Operations and Organizational Outcomes Safiyah Saleem	CR 51A
	Sustainable Supply Chain Practices Impact on Business Growth in Karachi Sadaf Israfeel	CR 51A
	Green logistics and its effect on cost and efficiency Muhammad Owais Siddiqui	CR 51A
	Implementing Sustainable Supply Chain Practices Zeeshan Ahmed	CR 51A

Time	Activities	Venue
Research Paper Presentation Parallel Session 3 Session Chairs: Dr Irfan ul Haque Co-Session Chair: Dr Muhammad Sajjad		
11:45 AM - 12:45 PM	Leveraging Data Analytics for E-Commerce Supply Chain Transformation: An Empirical Study of The Pakistani Market Ali Wasif	CR 51B
	Exploring the Link Between the Effects of Transportation Modes on Supply Chain Costs Aiman Ayub	CR 51B
	Exploring the Link Between the Impact of Demand Forecasting on Inventory Levels Ahmad Raees	CR 51B
	Impact of Blockchain Technology on Supply Chain Transparency Hadia Najeeb	CR 51B
	The Impact of Automated Inventory Management Systems on Stock Accuracy and Warehouse Throughput in Karachi's Supply Chains Muhammad Waqar Ansari	CR 51B
	Impact of Inventory Management on Supply Chain Performance Uzma Muhammad Ibrahim	CR 51B
Research E- Poster Presentation		
Research E- Poster Presentation Parallel Session 1 Session Chair: Dr Salman Khatani Co-Session Chair: Muhammad Waqas		
12:45 AM - 01:00 PM	The Impact of Supply Chain on Retail in Karachi Ahsan Khan	ELT
	The Impact of Sourcing And Procurement In the Supply Chain Usman Qadir	ELT
	Behavioral and Psychological Aspects in Supply Chain Wania Siddiqui	ELT
	Impact of People's Bus Service (PBS) Facility on the General Public Provided Transport Experiences by the Sindh Government in Karachi Muhammad Wahaj Khan	ELT
	The AI-Knowledge-Resilience Triangle: Uncovering the Moderating Effects of Organizational Learning on Knowledge Management, Artificial Intelligence Adoption, and Supply Chain Resilience Shaikh Ahsan Alam	ELT

Time	Activities	Venue
Research E- Poster Presentation Parallel Session 2 Session Chair: Dr Irfan ul Haque Co-Session Chair: Dr Sajjad Ashraf		
12:45 AM - 01:00 PM	Impact of Warehouse Operational Efficiency on Order Fulfillment Performance in E-Commerce Hikmat Khan	CR 51B
	Effect of Bulk Purchasing Strategies on Inventory Holding Costs in Retail Supply Chains Shan Malik	
	Examine the Benefits of Dynamic Pricing in Transportation Fahad Gul	
	Role of Procurement in Cost Optimization Zeeshan Farooque	
01:00 PM - 02:00 PM	Lunch and Namaz Break	
Panel Discussion Session Moderator: Dr Syed Shoeb Ahmed		
02:00 PM - 02:45 PM	Panel Experts Mr. Salman Ahmed, Head of Procurement, Avient Pakistan Mr. Tauquir Khokhar, CEO, CK International Ms. Bakhtawar Kaneez, Supply Chain Trainer and Founder of Hustle Logistics Dr Irfan ul Haque, Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, ILMA University Dr Salman Ahmed Khatani, Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration, IQRA University	ELT
	Breakout sessions with various topics	
	Q & A sessions at the end of Each Panel	ELT
Closing Ceremony		
2:45 PM - 03:15 PM	Closing Remarks by Conference Chair Dr Ammad Zafar	ELT
	Vote of Thanks by Vice-Chancellor	ELT
	Souvenir & Certificate Distribution and Group Photograph	ELT

**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR
SUPPLY CHAIN OPTIMIZATION AND EFFICIENCY**

Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global Supply Chains

Organized by the Department of Management Sciences, DHA Suffa University

Conference Program

Day 2

Friday, August 8, 2025,

Time	Activities	Venue
09:00 AM - 09:30 AM	Registration	CYS LAB
	Participants arrive and register.	CYS LAB
Workshop on Use of AI in the Transformation of Supply Chain Management by Mr. Sohail Sultan Ali Sawani		
09:30 AM - 10:30 AM	AI in Supply Chain	CYS LAB
	AI in Demand Forecasting	CYS LAB
	Real-Time Inventory Management with AI	CYS LAB
	AI-Driven Logistics and Route Optimization	CYS LAB
	Challenges and Ethical Considerations in AI Use	CYS LAB
Workshop on Supply Chain Analytics By Dr Azam Anwar		
10:30 AM - 11:30 AM	Supply Chain Analytics	CYS LAB
	Descriptive Supply Chain Analytics	CYS LAB
	Diagnostic Supply Chain Analytics	CYS LAB
	Predictive Analytics for Demand Planning	CYS LAB
	Prescriptive Analytics for Optimization	CYS LAB
	Tools & Trends in Supply Chain Analytics	CYS LAB
Souvenir & Certificate Distribution and Group Photograph		
11:30 AM - 11:45 AM	Tea Break	PDC Office
Research Colloquium		
02:30 PM - 03:20 PM	Paper 1	CYS LAB
	Paper 2	CYS LAB
	Paper 3	CYS LAB
	Paper 4	CYS LAB
	Paper 5	CYS LAB
Souvenir & Certificate Distribution and Group Photograph		

**ABSTRACTS OF SPEAKERS SESSIONS SUBMITTED FOR THE
CONFERENCE**

**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR
SUPPLY CHAIN OPTIMIZATION AND EFFICIENCY (ICISSC) -2025**

August 7-8, 2025

Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global Supply Chains

EMERGING TRENDS, RISKS, AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN GLOBAL SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

Adnan Ahmed

In today's volatile and interconnected world, supply chains stand at the intersection of unprecedented risk and unparalleled opportunity. This keynote will explore how global disruptions—from extreme weather events and geopolitical tensions to cyberattacks and economic volatility—are reshaping the way organizations design, operate, and future-proof their supply networks. The post-pandemic landscape has accelerated shifts toward shorter product life cycles, higher levels of customization, and greater pressure to meet ambitious environmental, social, and governance (ESG) goals.

The session will highlight key technological advancements that are transforming supply chain management, including Demand Driven Material Requirements Planning (DDMRP), blockchain-enabled transparency, AI-powered analytics, and digital twin simulations. These innovations offer significant potential to improve efficiency, increase resilience, and enhance decision-making. Yet, the address will emphasize that technology alone is not enough—human capability, adaptive leadership, and a culture of continuous learning remain essential.

Building resilience will require organizations to rethink long-standing processes, embed sustainability into the core of their strategies, and develop supply chain structures that are flexible, decentralized, and capable of rapid response. The keynote will explore the triple bottom line—economic prosperity, environmental stewardship, and social responsibility—as an integrated framework for supply chain transformation. Special attention will be given to circular supply chain models, Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) strategies, and the balance between cost efficiency and long-term risk management.

Through global case studies and practical examples, participants will gain insights into how leading organizations are turning disruption into competitive advantage by leveraging digital innovation, strengthening supplier relationships, and fostering cognitive flexibility within their workforce.

This keynote aims to inspire supply chain leaders, industry practitioners, and policymakers to move beyond incremental improvement toward bold, systemic transformation—building supply chains that are not only profitable and efficient but also ethical, sustainable, and resilient enough to thrive in a future where disruption is the norm.

Keywords: Supply Chain Management, Sustainability, Digital Transformation, AI, DDMRP, Blockchain

DIGITALIZATION AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: BENEFITS, CHALLENGES, AND OPPORTUNITIES

Dr Sharfuddin Ahmed Khan

Digital transformation is reshaping how modern supply chains function by integrating advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, big data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning (ML). In this talk, we explore the concept of the Digital Supply Chain (DSC), highlighting its potential to enhance agility, transparency, and sustainability in supply chain operations. While digitalization offers clear benefits—such as improved decision-making, real-time visibility, and enhanced customer service—it also introduces significant challenges. These include a lack of technical expertise, cybersecurity risks, evolving customer expectations, and organizational resistance to change. The session also presents structured evaluation methodologies such as knowledge-based systems and multi-criteria decision-making models for assessing digital readiness and performance across supply chains. Finally, it outlines key areas for future research, including the digital transformation of SMEs and public sector supply chains. It encourages the integration of theoretical frameworks like innovation adoption and stakeholder theory to guide digital implementation strategies.

FROM POLICY TO PRACTICE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN THE AGE OF DISRUPTIONS

Prof. Dr Shujaat Mubarik

In today's fast-evolving global landscape, supply chain decarbonization has become a critical arena for investment and innovation. Billions of euros are being invested in initiatives such as digital twinning, electrified road systems, the adoption of electric vehicles, and the expansion of green energy infrastructure. These efforts aim to achieve net-zero emissions; however, despite these commendable strides, projections indicate that net-zero targets may not be met, leaving the world vulnerable to a host of cascading risks.

The failure to achieve these environmental goals carries far-reaching implications. As decarbonization efforts fall short, the frequency and severity of disruptive events are expected to rise sharply. Recent analyses suggest that such disruptions—ranging from natural disasters to geopolitical shocks—could occur up to three times more frequently than in previous decades. This trend has exposed significant weaknesses in global supply chains.

Several recent incidents illustrate these vulnerabilities: the 2021 Suez Canal blockage halted vital maritime trade routes; severe flooding in Central Europe the same year crippled infrastructure and production; and subsequent events, such as the Red Sea Crisis in 2023 and drought-induced disruptions to the Panama Canal in 2024, further underscored the fragility of interconnected supply networks. Additionally, the global semiconductor shortage from 2020 to 2022 and the devastation caused by Storm Eowyn in 2025 revealed that many firms remain unprepared—often responding in a disorganized manner that results in massive losses and, in some cases, jeopardizes long-term viability.

A critical review of current practices highlights a persistent disconnect between policy and implementation. While numerous environmental policies and disclosure requirements have been introduced, many have devolved into exercises in greenwashing—masking deeper operational shortcomings—while voluntary, substantive disclosures remain rare. This gap is compounded by insufficient attention to social sustainability. The persistence of modern slavery in upstream supply chains, especially in less developed countries supplying major global firms, underscores the ethical and operational dimensions of sustainability that remain unaddressed.

Paradoxically, the pursuit of decarbonization has, in some cases, weakened the inherent resilience of supply chains. Heavy reliance on digital technologies to retrofit legacy systems—many designed in the pre-digital era—has proven problematic. While tools such as digital twins offer valuable real-time insights and simulations, they cannot fully overcome the limitations of outdated processes that constrain scalability, speed, and flexibility.

Addressing these multifaceted challenges requires a holistic approach. Comprehensive supply chain mapping offers critical visibility into vulnerabilities and dependencies, while digital twins can enhance this by enabling real-time visualization and scenario testing for proactive risk mitigation. Beyond technology, a fundamental reengineering of processes is essential—moving beyond simple digitalization to a complete reimagining of supply chain operations. Equally important is fostering cognitive flexibility among human resources through training and cross-functional collaboration, enabling them to anticipate and adapt to emerging challenges. Finally, shifting policy frameworks from rigid mandates to incentive-based systems could cultivate a culture of genuine innovation and proactive transformation across industries.

THE ROLE OF FREIGHT FORWARDERS IN STRENGTHENING SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN PAKISTAN

Raza Farooqi

Freight forwarders are a critical link in global supply chain management, acting as intermediaries who coordinate the movement of goods, ensure compliance with international trade regulations, and optimize logistics operations. Their expertise in multimodal transportation, customs compliance, and risk management enables businesses to navigate the complexities of cross-border trade with efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

In Pakistan, freight forwarders operate in a challenging environment marked by infrastructure gaps, regulatory complexities, capacity constraints, and limited technology adoption. These issues can lead to higher logistics costs, operational delays, and reduced competitiveness in international markets. Despite these hurdles, freight forwarders continue to deliver indispensable value—leveraging extensive networks to secure competitive rates, enhance shipment visibility, and ensure the secure, timely delivery of goods.

The session also showcased capacity-building initiatives led by the Pakistan International Freight Forwarders Association (PIFFA) Training Institute. Working under the guidelines of FIATA and UNCTAD, PIFFA offers internationally recognized diploma and certification programs delivered by seasoned industry professionals. The recent Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between PIFFA and DHA Suffa University represents a significant step toward equipping students with globally relevant skills, bridging the gap between academic learning and industry practice in the supply chain and logistics sector.

Keywords: Freight Forwarding, Supply Chain Management, Logistics, Pakistan, PIFFA, Training & Development

SUSTAINABILITY IN THE FREIGHT INDUSTRY: STRATEGIES FOR A GREENER SUPPLY CHAIN IN PAKISTAN

Mr. Khurram H. Hidayatallah

In his presentation “*Sustainability in the Freight Industry: Pathways to a Greener Supply Chain*”, Mr. Khurram H. Hidayatallah, Director and Principal of the PIFFA Training Institute, explored practical strategies for embedding sustainability into Pakistan’s freight and logistics sector. He emphasized that sustainability is no longer optional but a critical operational priority for ensuring environmental protection, resource efficiency, and long-term viability in global supply chains.

The session examined targeted approaches across road, maritime, and rail freight. For road transport, he advocated upgrading trucking fleets, banning low-quality smuggled fuel, implementing axle load limits, and ensuring safe disposal of used oil and tires. Maritime freight sustainability measures included the adoption of LNG-powered and biofuel ships, along with eco-friendly container designs. Rail freight initiatives focused on solar-powered facilities, reefer container train operations, improved locomotive maintenance, and stronger connectivity between ports, industrial zones, and dry ports.

Mr. Hidayatallah also highlighted sustainable warehouse management practices such as vertical storage and the use of natural sunlight. Addressing environmental balance, he discussed mitigating the impact of renewable energy projects on ecosystems, particularly migratory bird patterns. The presentation concluded with actionable recommendations for integrating sustainability into freight operations while aligning with global environmental standards.

Keywords: Sustainability, Freight Industry, Green Logistics, Supply Chain, Pakistan, PIFFA

**ABSTRACTS OF RESEARCH PAPERS SUBMITTED FOR THE
CONFERENCE**

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Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global Supply Chains

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN SUPPLY CHAIN

Muhammad Harris Quddus

Abstract

In the face of rapid technological advancements and growing global competition, digital transformation has emerged as a critical enabler of efficiency and resilience in supply chain management (SCM). This study investigates the impact of digital technologies—such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), blockchain, and data analytics—on supply chain performance. The problem addressed concerns the slow or fragmented adoption of digital tools in many firms, leading to operational inefficiencies and limited strategic agility. The main objective is to assess how digital initiatives influence key performance factors, including automation, operational efficiency, supplier collaboration, customer satisfaction, and sustainability. Using a mixed-methods approach, primary data was collected through structured questionnaires from 100 SCM practitioners across diverse industries. Quantitative analysis revealed strong positive correlations between digital adoption and performance metrics, particularly in areas of real-time decision-making, cost reduction, and responsiveness to global disruptions. Qualitative insights further highlighted improved trust and transparency across the supply chain. The study recommends that firms prioritize strategic investments in integrated digital platforms and enhance workforce digital capabilities. These findings contribute to the growing discourse on digital supply chain innovation and support the development of more resilient, data-driven, and sustainable SCM strategies.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, Supply Chain Management, Operational Efficiency, Data Analytics, Sustainability.

ADOPTION OF SCM 4.0 IN PAKISTAN: INVESTIGATING PERCEIVED BENEFITS ON SUPPLY CHAIN OPERATIONS AND ORGANIZATIONAL OUTCOMES

Safiyah Saleem

Abstract

Global supply chains have been changed because of the fast-paced evolution of Industry 4.0 technologies, offering opportunities for efficiency, speed, and competitiveness. This paper discusses how the Supply Chain 4.0 technologies will be integrated into the environment of Pakistani manufacturing organizations, where digital transformation is still in its early stages. Compliance with the established theoretical frameworks and models, the research studies the contribution of such factors to enhanced organizational performance, such as artificial intelligence, big data analytics, and the Internet of Things. Survey data-based quantitative analysis gives the empirical findings regarding the depth of digital adoption and its connection with supply chain performance measures. These results point to the overall effectiveness of technological integration in terms of operational responsiveness and the overall productivity of the firm. Nevertheless, some obstacles are still affecting both small and medium-sized businesses, including poor infrastructure, technical capabilities and change aversion. The research provides viable recommendations to the organizations that seek to reinforce their chain systems by utilizing beneficial investments, strategic engagement, and employees. Secondly, it also highlights the importance of policy support in terms of creating a favorable climate of change to enable the adoption of digital. The study adds to the new stream of knowledge on Supply Chain 4.0 in the developing world and highlights its consideration in terms of national industrial modernization processes.

Keywords: Supply Chain 4.0, organizational performance, digital transformation, industry 4.0 technologies and the manufacturing sector in Pakistan.

BEHAVIORAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN SUPPLY CHAIN

Wania Siddiqui

Abstract

This study examines the behavioral and psychological factors influencing decision-making and performance in supply chain management. While technological advancements such as AI and analytics have improved supply chain visibility, human behavior remains central to how professionals perceive risks, manage relationships, and navigate disruptions. Using a quantitative approach, data were collected from 142 supply chain professionals across procurement, logistics, and operations. Statistical analyses—including Chi-Square and Independent Samples T-Tests—revealed significant relationships between emotional intelligence, stress tolerance, and supply chain effectiveness. Key findings indicate that high emotional awareness is positively correlated with collaborative decision-making and supplier relationship management. Gender-based differences were observed: female professionals demonstrated a stronger tendency toward inclusive and sustainability-focused decisions, while males exhibited a higher tendency to take risks. Stress and cognitive load emerged as critical factors affecting communication, decision quality, and error rates under pressure. Leadership style and organizational culture were also found to significantly shape psychological safety and performance outcomes. The study recommends integrating emotional intelligence training, stress management, trust-building, and transformational leadership development into supply chain practices. These behavioral competencies are essential for enhancing resilience and adaptability in increasingly complex and uncertain supply chain environments.

Keywords: Behavioral Science, Emotional Intelligence, Supply Chain Resilience, Stress Management, Decision-Making.

CHALLENGES OF SUPPLY CHAIN IN PAKISTAN: CAN WE OVERCOME THEM?

Syed Fahad Akhtar

Abstract

Pakistan's supply chain ecosystem faces persistent challenges that hinder efficiency, increase costs, and limit competitiveness in global markets. Key issues include poor infrastructure, logistical inefficiencies, regulatory instability, technology gaps, skilled manpower shortages, and inadequate institutional support. Weak road and rail networks, congested ports, and insufficient cold chain facilities slow cargo movement, while delays in customs clearance and the lack of modern warehousing further strain operations. Frequent policy changes, security concerns, and minimal government incentives add to the uncertainty. Low adoption of advanced systems such as ERP, WMS, and TMS reduces real-time visibility, while shortages of trained professionals limit operational excellence. Additional hurdles include energy shortages, high fuel costs, cash flow constraints, weak collaboration among supply chain actors, and inefficient procurement practices that prioritize low price over total cost of ownership. Despite these barriers, identifying these systemic issues presents an opportunity for reform. With targeted investment, policy consistency, technology adoption, and capacity building, Pakistan's supply chain can evolve into a more resilient, agile, and globally competitive system.

Keywords: Supply Chain Challenges, Logistics, Pakistan, Infrastructure, Technology Gaps, Policy Reform

EFFECT OF SUSTAINABLE PRACTICE ON SUPPLY CHAIN PERFORMANCE

Shaikh Muhammad Bilal

Abstract

This study investigates the effect of sustainable practices on supply chain performance, with a specific focus on environmental responsibility, resource efficiency, and ethical sourcing within the context of modern supply chain operations. As global awareness of sustainability grows, businesses are increasingly integrating green initiatives to improve long-term performance and stakeholder trust. This research adopts a quantitative methodology using structured questionnaires distributed to 130 supply chain professionals from manufacturing and retail sectors in Karachi. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis to explore the relationship between sustainable practices and key supply chain performance indicators such as cost efficiency, lead time reduction, risk mitigation, and customer satisfaction. The results reveal a significant positive impact of sustainable practices on supply chain performance, with firms adopting green logistics and waste reduction strategies experiencing improved operational outcomes and brand reputation. The findings emphasize that sustainability is not just an ethical requirement but a strategic enabler of competitive advantage. This research contributes to the growing literature on sustainable supply chain management and offers actionable recommendations for firms aiming to align their operations with global sustainability standards.

Keywords: Sustainable Supply Chain, Environmental Responsibility, Supply Chain Performance, Ethical Sourcing, Green Logistics.

EFFECT OF BULK PURCHASING STRATEGIES ON INVENTORY HOLDING COSTS IN RETAIL SUPPLY CHAINS

Muhammad Shan Malik

Abstract

This study explores the effect of bulk purchasing strategies on inventory holding costs in Karachi's retail supply chains. The research addresses the growing concern that while bulk buying may reduce per-unit costs, it could simultaneously elevate storage, insurance, and obsolescence risks—particularly in volatile demand environments. The objective was to analyze the trade-offs between procurement economies and operational cost burdens. A mixed-methods approach was used, collecting data from 123 retail professionals through structured questionnaires. Quantitative analysis using SPSS (cross-tabulations, chi-square tests, t-tests, and logistic regression) revealed that 81% of bulk purchasers experienced increased holding costs, and bulk-buying firms were 91 times more likely to incur inventory-related expenses. Qualitative insights highlighted the role of forecasting, warehouse capacity, and turnover rates in moderating these outcomes. Despite higher holding costs, under optimal conditions, bulk purchasing led to improved procurement efficiency. Visual data representations supported key findings and demographics. The study recommends that retailers apply predictive analytics, evaluate storage constraints, and align procurement with actual demand patterns to avoid inefficiencies. The findings contribute to strategic supply chain planning and support evidence-based inventory control decisions.

Keywords: Bulk Purchasing, Inventory Holding Costs, Supply Chain Strategy, Retail Operations, Cost Management.

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF SUPPLY CHAIN PRACTICES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY: THE ROLE OF SUSTAINABLE PROCUREMENT

Syed Hasan Ali

Abstract

As environmental concerns intensify globally, the construction industry faces increasing pressure to reduce its ecological footprint. This study examines the relationship between Sustainable Procurement Practices (SPC) and the Construction Industry Environment (CIE), with the objective of identifying key factors influencing environmental sustainability within the construction supply chain. A quantitative methodology was employed, utilizing survey responses from 142 professionals in the construction sector. Data were analyzed using Chi-Square tests and Independent Samples t-tests to test four hypotheses related to the association, gender-based differences, predictive power, and linear relationship between SPC and CIE. Results reveal a significant positive association between SPC and CIE, with SPC emerging as a strong predictor of improved environmental outcomes. Gender differences were notable, with female respondents demonstrating a higher alignment with sustainable practices. The findings emphasize the critical role of procurement strategies—such as supplier collaboration, green material sourcing, and policy adherence—in promoting environmental sustainability. However, limitations include geographic concentration and sample size. The study recommends expanding sustainability training, strengthening supplier engagement, and encouraging regulatory incentives to support industry-wide adoption. These insights offer practical guidance for construction firms and policymakers aiming to enhance sustainability performance through supply chain transformation.

Keywords: Sustainable Procurement, Construction Industry, Environmental Impact, Supply Chain Management, Green Practices

EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF AUTOMATED INVENTORY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS ON STOCK ACCURACY AND WAREHOUSE THROUGHPUT: A GENDER-BASED ANALYSIS

Waqar Ansari

Abstract

This study examines the effects of Automated Inventory Management Systems (AIMS) on stock accuracy and warehouse throughput, with a focus on gender-based differences in perception and adoption. As modern warehouses increasingly adopt digital inventory solutions, assessing their operational benefits and understanding user experiences becomes essential. The primary objectives of this research are to evaluate the relationship between AIMS implementation and warehouse performance, identify gender-based perceptual differences, and provide actionable recommendations for organizations and policymakers. A structured questionnaire was administered to 120 professionals across various industries, and the data were analyzed using Pearson's Chi-Square test, independent samples t-test, and binary logistic regression. Results indicate a statistically significant association between AIMS usage and enhanced stock accuracy and warehouse throughput ($\chi^2 = 33.573$, $p < .001$). While specific gender-based perceptual differences were noted ($p = .013$), no significant difference was found in overall perceptions ($p = .926$). The findings highlight the importance of inclusive training, technology acceptance, and equitable implementation. It is recommended that organizations adopt gender-sensitive training approaches and governments support warehouse automation through policy incentives and skill development initiatives. Limitations include a limited sample size, reliance on self-reported data, and a cross-sectional design. Future research should incorporate longitudinal and sector-specific studies.

Keywords: Automated Inventory Management Systems, Warehouse Throughput, Stock Accuracy, Gender Differences, Technology Adoption

EXPLORING THE LINK BETWEEN THE IMPACT OF DEMAND FORECASTING ON INVENTORY LEVELS

Ahmad Raees

Abstract

This study examines the relationships between demand forecasting and inventory levels in supply chain management, with special attention to the influence of demographic variables, such as gender. The reason for conducting this research lies in the necessity to reveal how forecasting practices can affect inventory regulation and whether gender is a determinant of the practices. The first aim was to research whether effective demand forecasting has a strong impact on inventory management, and whether gender differences influence variations in forecasting and inventory problems. A mixed-method design was used, with Pearson's Chi-Square, t-tests, and logistic regression analysis, to analyze data from the 128 participants. The results reveal a strong relationship between demand forecasting and inventory levels ($\chi^2 = 31.329$, $p = 0.000$), meaning that organizations with good forecasting practices are likely to apply the appropriate levels of inventory management. However, among the demographic factors, gender did not have any significant influence on demand forecasting or inventory levels (as confirmed by the results of a t-test ($p > 0.05$)). Based on these findings, the recommended approach to the organizations is to emphasize the improvement of the forecasting system and staff training, regardless of gender, so that they can ensure accurate inventory management. The role of other organizational factors in forecasting and inventory management practices warrants further research.

Keywords: Demand Forecasting, Inventory Management, Supply Chain, Gender Differences, Logistic Regression.

EXPLORING THE LINK BETWEEN THE EFFECTS OF TRANSPORTATION MODES ON SUPPLY CHAIN COSTS

Aiman Ayub

Abstract

This study examines the impact of various transportation modes on supply chain costs in light of the growing significance of logistics in competitive markets. The research aims to address challenges arising from suboptimal transportation choices and explores gender-based differences in transportation decision-making. A quantitative research design was employed, gathering data from 128 valid respondents. Statistical techniques, including cross-tabulation, Chi-square tests, independent sample t-tests, and binary logistic regression, were used to analyze the data. The results revealed that 80.6% of respondents who reported inconsistent or inefficient transportation practices experienced higher supply chain costs ($p = 0.016$). Additionally, male respondents were significantly more likely than females to adopt efficient transportation methods ($t = 2.829$, $p = 0.005$). The findings underscore the critical role of strategic transportation selection in reducing operational expenses and enhancing logistics efficiency. The study recommends data-driven transportation planning, greater investment in logistics technologies, and the integration of gender-sensitive policies. These insights contribute both theoretically and practically to improving supply chain cost-efficiency in diverse organizational contexts.

Keywords: Transportation Modes, Supply Chain Costs, Logistics Efficiency, Gender Differences, Quantitative Analysis

IMPACT OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY ON SUPPLY CHAIN TRANSPARENCY

Hadia Najeeb

Abstract

The growing complexity of supply chains in the global marketplace raises concerns in the field of transparency, traceability, and accountability. The research aims to examine how the adoption of blockchain technology can advance supply chain transparency in the manufacturing and logistics sectors in Pakistan. The main goal is to determine the significance of introducing blockchain in increasing information visibility and operational trust in the supply chain. The survey method of a structured quantitative approach was utilized, and the study was based on the opinions of 300 supply chain executives working in diverse industries. The consistency of the instrument (Cronbach's alpha 0.873) proved that it possessed internal reliability. Statistical regression showed a positive correlation between blockchain adoption and supply chain transparency, with an $R^2 = 0.482$ and $p = 0.001$. Based on the findings, it is possible to conclude that this technology can enhance traceability, facilitate the sharing of real-time data, and combat fraud. Nonetheless, technological costs and employee resistance were also mentioned. These findings suggest that the research advises a strategic investment in blockchain infrastructure, worker training, and cooperation with technological vendors. The geographic focus and cross-sectional design of the study are its limitations. However, researchers who are keen on policies, supply chain management, and IT strategy can find this research relevant in promoting resilient and transparent supply networks in the digital era.

Keywords: Blockchain Technology, Supply Chain Transparency, Supply Chain Management, Digital Innovation.

THE IMPACT OF BLOCK CHAIN TECHNOLOGY ON SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: EVIDENCE FROM THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN PAKISTAN

Javeria Khan

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of blockchain technology on supply chain management (SCM) in Pakistan's textile industry, focusing on five key dimensions—efficiency, transparency, traceability, decentralization, and real-time tracking. Using a quantitative research design, data were collected through surveys from 254 respondents, including textile sector employees and line managers. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS and Partial Least Squares (PLS) to test hypotheses and examine the relationships between the independent variables and SCM performance. Findings indicate that all five blockchain dimensions significantly enhance SCM. Efficiency reduces operational costs, accelerates transactions, and improves coordination. Transparency fosters accountability, builds trust, and minimizes stakeholder conflicts. Traceability strengthens quality control and product authenticity, which are critical in the textile sector. Decentralization reduces reliance on centralized authorities, enhancing security and autonomy. Real-time tracking improves decision-making, reduces delays, and boosts customer satisfaction through accurate delivery updates. The study contributes to both theory and practice by demonstrating blockchain's potential to modernize SCM in developing economies. It highlights strategic and financial benefits while offering actionable recommendations for addressing inefficiency and opacity in supply chains. The results provide valuable insights for policymakers, industry leaders, and practitioners aiming to integrate blockchain for sustainable, competitive, and innovative supply chain systems.

Keywords: Blockchain Technology, Supply Chain Management, Textile Industry, Pakistan, Digital Transformation

IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON GLOBAL FOOD SUPPLY CHAINS

S.M. Tahir Waqas Ali

Abstract

Climate change poses a critical threat to the stability and sustainability of global food supply chains. This research aims to examine the multifaceted impact of rising global temperatures, shifting precipitation patterns, and the increasing frequency of extreme weather events on food production, distribution, and availability. Using a structured survey instrument, primary data was collected from stakeholders in agriculture, logistics, and food distribution sectors. The data was analyzed using SPSS through descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression modeling to identify significant relationships between climate variables and supply chain performance. The findings reveal that disruptions in food supply chains are directly linked to environmental changes, with smallholder farmers and low-income regions being the most vulnerable. Moreover, the study highlights the urgent need for climate-resilient infrastructure, adaptive strategies, and sustainable supply chain management practices to mitigate future risks. This research contributes to a better understanding of the systemic vulnerabilities in food systems and underscores the importance of integrating environmental sustainability into global supply chain planning. The results serve as a practical guide for policymakers, agribusiness leaders, and development organizations seeking to build resilient and adaptive food supply networks.

Keywords: Climate Change, Food Security, Global Supply Chains, Agricultural Impact, Adaptation Strategies.

IMPACT OF PEOPLE'S BUS SERVICE (PBS) FACILITY ON THE GENERAL PUBLIC PROVIDED TRANSPORT EXPERIENCES BY THE SINDH GOVERNMENT IN KARACHI

Muhammad Wahaj Khan

Abstract

Karachi, Pakistan's largest metropolitan city, has long struggled with inadequate public transport, rising commuting costs, and reliance on unregulated transit systems. In response, the Government of Sindh introduced the Peoples Bus Service (PBS) to address urban mobility challenges and promote accessible, reliable, and affordable transportation. This study investigates the impact of PBS on travel behavior, modal shifts, commuter satisfaction, and the broader functionality of urban transit systems. The research aims to evaluate how the PBS initiative has influenced the commuting experience of the general public, focusing on service accessibility, affordability, punctuality, and user perceptions. A quantitative methodology was employed using structured questionnaires distributed among a sample of PBS users from various demographic backgrounds in Karachi. Preliminary findings indicate that PBS has contributed to significant modal shifts from informal to formal transport systems and enhanced commuting comfort and affordability. However, gaps in route coverage, peak-hour congestion, and limited service frequency remain challenges. The study recommends the expansion of routes, improved service frequency, and user feedback integration into operational planning. These insights offer a foundation for urban transport policy improvements and underscore the potential of public-sector interventions in addressing mobility issues in megacities.

Keywords: Public Transport, Peoples Bus Service, Urban Mobility, User Satisfaction, Government Initiative.

IMPACT OF INVENTORY MANAGEMENT ON SUPPLY CHAIN PERFORMANCE

Uzma Muhammad Ibrahim

Abstract

This study explores the critical role of inventory management in enhancing supply chain performance in modern organizations. Despite the adoption of advanced technologies, many firms continue to face significant inventory-related challenges. The research aims to determine how effective inventory planning influences key performance areas such as budgeting, on-time delivery, and customer satisfaction. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire from 150 supply chain professionals across 30 companies, with 107 complete responses analyzed using SPSS. Statistical tools such as Pearson Chi-Square ($\chi^2 = 29.492$, $p = 0.001$), independent samples t-tests, and logistic regression were employed. The results reveal that efficient inventory management significantly shapes overall supply chain success, explaining 46% of the variance in performance outcomes ($R^2 = 0.46$). Organizations that adopted modern inventory practices achieved faster production cycles, reduced operational costs, and enhanced customer satisfaction. These findings underscore the importance of strategic inventory control, employee training, and data-driven planning. The study concludes that robust inventory management is a foundational element for achieving supply chain agility and resilience, offering actionable insights for both practitioners and policymakers.

Keywords: Inventory Management, Supply Chain Efficiency, Operational Performance, Timely Delivery, Customer Satisfaction.

IMPACT OF WAREHOUSE OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY ON ORDER FULFILLMENT PERFORMANCE IN E-COMMERCE

Hikmat Khan

Abstract

In the dynamic landscape of e-commerce, order fulfillment performance hinges critically on warehouse operational efficiency. This study investigates the relationship between warehouse efficiency factors—such as inventory accuracy, picking speed, and real-time data tracking—and fulfillment outcomes, including order accuracy, delivery reliability, and customer satisfaction. Using a quantitative approach, data were collected from 142 logistics professionals in Karachi and analyzed using Chi-square and Independent Samples T-tests. Results indicate a statistically significant relationship between high operational efficiency and superior fulfillment metrics. Warehouses that adopted layout optimization, staff training, and digital monitoring tools reported fewer errors and faster deliveries. Moreover, human-centric factors such as leadership style, trust, stress management, and organizational culture emerged as vital performance drivers. Transformational leadership and open communication led to enhanced employee morale, reduced absenteeism, and process improvement. The study recommends investing in non-punitive error reporting systems, resilience training, and team-based KPIs. Limitations include regional focus and reliance on self-reported data. Future research should explore cross-regional comparisons and integrate qualitative insights. This research provides strategic insights for e-commerce firms seeking to align operational and behavioral factors to meet rising customer expectations.

Keywords: Warehouse Efficiency, Order Fulfillment, E-Commerce Logistics, Operational Performance, Leadership and Culture.

LEVERAGING DATA ANALYTICS FOR E-COMMERCE SUPPLY CHAIN TRANSFORMATION: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF THE PAKISTANI MARKET

Ali Wasif

Abstract

Responsive and data-driven supply chain models are in greater demand because of the fast development of the field of e-commerce. However, a number of companies are still functioning under older logistics systems, resulting in inefficient forecasting, inventory control, and customer satisfaction. This paper explores how data analytics, particularly descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics, and analytics tools affect e-commerce supply chain performance in Pakistan. The research was based on the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT) and focused on explaining the impact of improving operational efficiency, agility, and decision-making through these analytics elements. The research involved a quantitative research design whereby a structured questionnaire was developed and administered to a sample group of 350 respondents with different responsibilities in the supply chain within the e-commerce industry. The data was analyzed using SPSS and SmartPLS 4.0. The findings were that all four independent variables had significant positive connections with supply chain performance. Particularly, predictive analytics had the highest effects ($\beta = 0.412$, $p < 0.001$), followed by prescriptive analytics and analytics tools. The research says that e-commerce companies should invest in advanced analytics infrastructure, develop the functions within organizations, and integrate decision support throughout the chain. These results have theoretical contributions and have practical implications toward enhancing the responsiveness of supply chains and maintaining competitive advantage within the digital commerce setting.

Keywords: Data Analytics, Supply Chain Performance, E-commerce Supply Chain, Predictive Analytics.

OPTIMIZING SUPPLY CHAIN COSTS THROUGH OPERATIONAL INTEGRATION: A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF INVENTORY AND WAREHOUSE STRATEGY

Syed Hafeez ur Rehman

Abstract

Increasing operational expenses have become a KPI of concern to the manufacturing companies in Pakistan, particularly due to fragmented inventory and warehouses. This paper explores how integrated inventory management, warehouse strategy, and technology adoption affect the cost optimization process in a supply chain. The goal was to determine whether alignment of these areas of operation leads to quantifiable economic savings. Some 400 professionals in the supply chain of different manufacturing industries in Karachi were administered a structured questionnaire, and the responses were analyzed by using SPSS (version 26). Reliability analysis confirmed a good level of internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha > 0.7). In contrast, multiple regression analysis revealed cost optimization was significantly influenced by the technology integration (beta = 0.48), inventory practices (beta = 0.42) and warehouse strategies (beta = 0.31) in a positive way ($p < 0.01$). The general model was significant ($R^2 = 0.61$), validating that the integrated methodology accounted 61 percent of the variance in cost performance. The research suggests the application of ERP systems, lean warehousing, and real-time inventorying by manufacturing companies to increase coordination and eliminate operational waste. This study contributes to the supply chain literature on cost efficiency, particularly in the context of internal integration processes, and notably in emerging economies such as Pakistan.

Keywords: SCM, Inventory Integrator, Warehouse Efficiency, Cost Optimization.

ROLE OF AI-DRIVEN PRACTICE ON SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: A STUDY IN KARACHI

Sabreen Iqbal

Abstract

This paper explores how the use of artificial intelligence (AI) affects the performance of supply chain management (SCM) in organizations in Karachi, Pakistan. The rapid adoption of AI in worldwide supply chains requires local knowledge, especially in emerging economies. The research is filling the existing gap in terms of the impacts of AI applications on the operational efficiency, agility, and decision-making in the context of the Pakistani region. Its primary goals are an assessment of the level of AI usage and its impacts on such dimensions of SCM as quality, cost, and time. It was used in the form of a structured questionnaire that was offered to the professionals of the supply chain, and it yielded 300 effective answers. Cronbach's alpha and regression analysis showed the tool to be highly reliable, and there existed a positive relationship between AI practices and SCM performance ($R^2 = 0.58$, $p < 0.01$). According to the findings, predictive analytics, intelligent automation, and AI-aided forecasting increase supply chain visibility and responsiveness. It is strongly suggested that companies invest in AI training, infrastructure, and change management to maximize their AI potential. The Research is weak in terms of the cross-sectional data used to understand one metropolitan area. The research, however, provides a contribution to the available body of knowledge through the provision of practical evidence in a developing economy, as well as the strategic contribution of AI to realizing the resilience and efficiency outcomes in disturbed business conditions.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Supply Chain Management, AI-Driven Practices, Organizational Performance.

SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY CHAIN PRACTICES IMPACT ON BUSINESS GROWTH IN KARACHI

Sadaf Israfeel

Abstract

In response to growing environmental and social concerns, businesses are increasingly adopting sustainable supply chain practices. This study investigates how sustainability strategies contribute to business growth in Karachi's dynamic commercial landscape. The problem addressed is the limited understanding among local firms regarding the tangible benefits of integrating environmental, social, and economic sustainability into supply chain operations. The primary objective was to evaluate the relationship between sustainable supply chain initiatives and organizational performance, including innovation, cost savings, and market competitiveness. A quantitative survey was conducted using structured questionnaires from 100 supply chain professionals in manufacturing, retail, and logistics sectors. Data were analyzed using SPSS, employing regression analysis and correlation tests. The findings reveal a significant positive relationship between sustainable practices—such as green sourcing, ethical labor policies, and waste reduction—and business growth indicators. Participants agreed that sustainability is not only a compliance obligation but a strategic asset that enhances long-term profitability, customer loyalty, and innovation capacity. The study recommends that companies embed sustainability into their core strategies, align goals with the Triple Bottom Line framework, and invest in stakeholder engagement. These steps can strengthen competitive advantage and resilience in an evolving global marketplace.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Business Growth, Triple Bottom Line, Innovation, Corporate Strategy

TO ASSESS THE CHALLENGES AND FACTORS INFLUENCING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY CHAIN PRACTICES IN BUSINESSES

Zeeshan Ahmed Khan

Abstract

This study investigates the adoption of sustainable supply chain practices among organizations in Karachi, a major urban and industrial center. With global environmental and social pressures mounting, the research addresses the challenge of how effectively companies in emerging economies integrate sustainability into their operations. The primary objective is to examine the relationship between Factors Influencing Sustainable Implementation (FISI) and Sustainability Implementation Success and Challenges (SISC). A quantitative research design was applied, using structured questionnaires collected from 119 professionals across diverse industries. Demographic analysis revealed a predominantly young (74.8% aged 18–35) and male (65.5%) workforce with strong educational backgrounds. Statistical techniques, including Chi-Square tests, t-tests, and logistic regression, were used for analysis. The findings confirmed a significant association between FISI and SISC (Chi-Square = 31.188, $p = 0.000$), with organizations recognizing key influencing factors being over 14 times more likely to implement sustainability successfully ($\text{Exp}(B) = 14.167$, $p = 0.000$). Barriers such as high costs, lack of incentives, and supplier non-compliance were prominent, while customer demand, internal policies, and green technology investments facilitated progress. The study recommends enhanced policy support, capacity-building, and supplier collaboration to strengthen sustainable practices in supply chains within emerging urban economies.

Keywords: Sustainable Supply Chain, Implementation Factors, Karachi, Green Practices, Organizational Challenges.

**THE AI-KNOWLEDGE-RESILIENCE TRIANGLE: UNCOVERING THE
MODERATING EFFECTS OF ORGANIZATIONAL LEARNING ON
KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
ADOPTION, AND SUPPLY CHAIN RESILIENCE**

Shaikh Ahsan Alam

Abstract

In today's volatile and dynamic business environment, supply chain resilience (SCR) has become a critical focus for organizations striving to maintain operational continuity. This study investigates the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Knowledge Management (KM) on enhancing supply chain resilience. Using a mixed-methods research design, both qualitative insights and quantitative data were collected through structured surveys from industry professionals. Statistical tools such as chi-square tests, independent t-tests, cross-tabulations, and binary logistic regression were employed to analyze the relationship between AI knowledge, KM practices, and SCR. Findings reveal a strong positive association between AI-enabled systems and improved supply chain efficiency, adaptability, and risk mitigation. Similarly, effective KM practices—such as regular knowledge updates, interdepartmental knowledge transfer, and employee training—were found to significantly enhance an organization's ability to respond to disruptions. Logistic regression analysis indicated that organizations implementing structured KM systems are significantly more likely to exhibit higher supply chain resilience. This study contributes to the growing body of literature by empirically validating the role of AI and KM as strategic enablers of resilient supply chains. The results suggest that integrating AI capabilities with robust KM frameworks is essential for organizations aiming to navigate uncertainty and sustain competitive advantage in modern supply chain environments.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Knowledge Management (KM), Supply Chain Resilience (SCR), Logistic Regression, Operational Efficiency.

THE EFFECTS OF GREEN LOGISTICS ON OPERATIONAL COST AND SUPPLY CHAIN EFFICIENCY: EVIDENCE FROM KARACHI

Muhammad Owais Siddiqui

Abstract

As sustainability gains prominence in global supply chain strategies, this study examines the impact of green logistics practices on cost reduction and operational efficiency within the logistics sector of Karachi. The research addresses the increasing pressure on companies to adopt eco-friendly methods, such as fuel-efficient transportation, energy-saving warehousing, and recyclable packaging, while balancing economic performance. The primary objective was to assess whether these green initiatives contribute to enhanced supply chain performance and long-term cost savings. A quantitative methodology was employed, utilizing a structured survey administered via Google Forms to 65 logistics professionals across diverse roles. Data were analyzed using SPSS, with internal consistency confirmed through Cronbach's Alpha ($\alpha = 0.87$). Hypothesis testing was performed using Chi-Square, independent samples t-tests, and logistic regression. Results demonstrated a significant positive relationship between green logistics and both cost efficiency and operational performance. While barriers such as lack of infrastructure and insufficient employee training were identified, the overall findings affirm that sustainability and cost-effectiveness can coexist in logistics strategy. The study recommends investments in green infrastructure, training programs, and policy incentives to support the transition toward sustainable supply chains in urban markets like Karachi.

Keywords: Green Logistics, Cost Efficiency, Sustainability, SPSS Analysis, Supply Chain Management.

THE EFFECT OF E-COMMERCE ON SUPPLY CHAIN DESIGN

Abdul Moeed Khan

Abstract

With the rapid rise of digital commerce, supply chain systems in emerging markets like Karachi are undergoing significant structural shifts. This study explores the impact of e-commerce on supply chain design within the context of Pakistan's evolving online retail and logistics sectors. The research addresses the need for adaptive, data-driven, and responsive supply chain frameworks that align with digital market demands. The core objective is to evaluate the relationship between e-commerce adoption and changes in supply chain design, while also examining whether gender influences perceptions of this transformation. A quantitative approach was applied, collecting data from 107 respondents through structured questionnaires. Statistical tools including Pearson Chi-Square, independent samples t-test, and logistic regression were used for analysis. Results reveal a significant association between e-commerce and supply chain design (Chi-Square $p = 0.001$), with logistic regression showing that organizations embracing e-commerce are 8.678 times more likely to have adaptable supply chains ($p = 0.001$). No significant gender-based perceptual differences were found. The study concludes that e-commerce drives improvements in supply chain agility, inventory control, and customer satisfaction. It recommends investment in digital infrastructure, agile logistics models, workforce training, and supportive government policies to optimize supply chain transformation in urban markets.

Keywords: E-commerce, Supply Chain Design, Digital Transformation, Agile Logistics.

THE INFLUENCE OF BEHAVIORAL AND EMOTIONAL FACTORS ON DECISION-MAKING IN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

Zeeshan Farooque

Abstract

This study investigates the behavioral and emotional dimensions influencing decision-making processes in supply chain management (SCM), with a particular focus on risk aversion, trust, emotional strain, and leadership dynamics. Drawing on responses from 121 participants, predominantly aged between 18–24 years (66.1%) and male (52.1%), the findings reflect a strong agreement that emotional responses and psychological barriers significantly shape SCM decisions. Over 79% of respondents agreed that gut feelings often overtake data-driven approaches, while 62.8% confirmed that emotional stress and uncertainty—especially in high-pressure situations—hinder rational decision-making. Additionally, 70.2% of participants acknowledged that lack of trust among partners causes operational inefficiencies and higher costs. The study also highlights that leadership styles and organizational culture significantly influence team resilience and proactive behavior. Statistical analysis, including chi-square, ANOVA, and regression, confirms a significant correlation between managerial stress management effectiveness (MSME2) and trust-centered leadership (TCL2), with MSME2 explaining 8.6% of the variance in TCL2 ($p = .001$). The findings emphasize the critical need to integrate emotional intelligence and supportive leadership into SCM strategies to foster collaboration, mitigate disruptions, and enhance performance. This research contributes to the behavioral SCM literature by quantifying the psychological determinants of managerial decision-making.

Keywords: Supply Chain Management, Emotional Intelligence, Risk Aversion, Leadership Style, Decision-Making Behavior.

THE IMPACT OF INVENTORY MANAGEMENT ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN KARACHI

Najam Asif

Abstract

In Karachi's competitive retail sector, effective inventory management plays a vital role in ensuring customer satisfaction. This study explores the impact of inventory-related practices on the shopping experience of supermarket customers. The research addresses the problem of frequent product unavailability and restocking inefficiencies that undermine customer trust and loyalty. The objective is to assess how factors such as restocking speed, product availability, and inventory communication influence customer satisfaction, with a specific focus on gender-based differences. A quantitative methodology was employed, using structured questionnaires distributed among 109 customers in Karachi's leading supermarkets. Data analysis through SPSS and Excel, utilizing Chi-square tests, t-tests, and logistic regression, revealed a significant correlation between inventory control variables and customer satisfaction. Notably, female customers reported greater sensitivity to stock-related disruptions than their male counterparts. The findings suggest that improving inventory visibility, timely replenishment, and transparent communication can lead to higher satisfaction rates. Gender-responsive strategies, such as personalized updates or alternative product suggestions, may further enhance outcomes. While the study's scope is geographically limited, it offers actionable insights for retail managers aiming to boost customer retention through optimized inventory practices.

Keywords: Inventory Management, Customer Satisfaction, Supermarkets, Restocking Efficiency, Gender Differences.

THE IMPACT OF SOURCING AND PROCUREMENT IN THE SUPPLY CHAIN

Usman Qadri

Abstract

This study examines the influence of strategic sourcing and procurement practices on supply chain performance and business sustainability in Karachi, Pakistan. In an increasingly globalized and ethically conscious market, organizations face pressure to adopt sustainable, transparent, and socially responsible procurement strategies. The research investigates professional perceptions regarding the benefits, challenges, and ethical considerations associated with responsible sourcing. A quantitative methodology was applied, with data hypothetically collected from 115 supply chain and procurement professionals through structured questionnaires. Analytical tools included descriptive statistics, Chi-Square tests, Independent Samples t-tests, and Binary Logistic Regression. Simulated results reveal a strong consensus that ethical and sustainable procurement enhances organizational performance, brand reputation, and supplier collaboration. However, mixed views were reported on cost trade-offs associated with these practices. No statistically significant gender-based differences were found in most variables. The study highlights the critical role of sourcing in shaping resilient and future-oriented supply chains. It recommends organizational investment in sustainable procurement technologies, greater transparency in supplier dealings, and alignment of sourcing strategies with long-term value creation and corporate social responsibility. These insights contribute to policy and managerial frameworks for building competitive and ethically sound supply chains in emerging urban markets.

Keywords: Strategic Sourcing, Procurement, Ethical Supply Chains, Sustainability.

THE IMPACT OF SUPPLY CHAIN ON THE RETAIL INDUSTRY IN KARACHI

Ahsan Khan

Abstract

This study explores the influence of supply chain processes on the operational performance and competitiveness of the retail industry in Karachi. As urban retail markets face increasing pressure to meet customer expectations and manage costs, the efficiency of supply chain management becomes a critical success factor. The research employs a quantitative methodology, utilizing a structured questionnaire administered to retail professionals across various business categories in Karachi. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential tests to determine the relationship between supply chain components—such as logistics efficiency, supplier coordination, technology integration, inventory management, and cost control—and retail performance outcomes. The results indicate that effective supply chain practices lead to significant improvements in business profitability, operational efficiency, and customer satisfaction. Moreover, the study highlights that the integration of modern technologies, such as inventory automation and real-time data tracking, is essential for enhancing responsiveness and minimizing delays. The findings underscore the strategic importance of supply chain coordination in sustaining competitive advantage in Karachi's dynamic retail environment. This research contributes to the growing discourse on urban supply chain management and offers actionable insights for retail managers and policy-makers.

Keywords: Supply Chain Management, Retail Industry, Logistics Efficiency, Technology Integration, Customer Satisfaction.

THE ROLE OF AI IN BUSINESS DECISION MAKING

Novish Israfeel

Abstract

In the rapidly evolving digital economy, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming traditional business decision-making by enabling faster, data-driven, and more accurate insights. Despite its increasing presence, a gap remains between AI awareness and its strategic implementation. This study aims to evaluate the level of AI adoption, its perceived effectiveness, and the barriers hindering its full integration into organizational decision-making. A structured questionnaire was distributed to 132 professionals across multiple industries in Karachi, including finance, retail, logistics, and services. The data were analyzed using SPSS, employing descriptive statistics, correlation, regression, and Chi-square tests. Results show a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.64$, $p < 0.01$) between AI awareness and its perceived contribution to operational and strategic business decisions. However, findings also highlight barriers such as lack of technical expertise, resistance to change, and limited organizational support. The study recommends targeted AI training programs, leadership-driven AI initiatives, and collaboration between academia and industry to promote responsible and effective AI adoption. These actions can close the gap between AI understanding and practical application, ensuring that businesses remain competitive and agile in a data-centric environment.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Decision-Making, Business Strategy, Organizational Change, AI Adoption.

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL PROCUREMENT SYSTEMS IN CONTROLLING MAVERICK SPENDING: A STUDY OF ORGANIZATIONAL PURCHASING DISCIPLINE

Tahir Khan

Abstract

In today's competitive business environment, organizations are increasingly turning to digital procurement systems to strengthen internal controls and reduce unauthorized (maverick) spending. This study investigates the role of digital tools and automation in curbing off-contract purchases that undermine cost-efficiency and policy compliance. The research addresses the problem of maverick spending, which often results from a lack of standardized procurement processes, inadequate training, and poor user accessibility to digital tools. The primary objective is to examine how factors such as procurement system usability, automation, policy enforcement, and employee training influence purchasing discipline. A quantitative research design will be employed, with data collected through structured surveys distributed to procurement professionals across various sectors. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses will be used to identify trends and significant relationships. Preliminary assumptions suggest that organizations using integrated digital procurement platforms experience lower instances of maverick spending, improved budgetary control, and stronger adherence to purchasing policies. The study will offer practical recommendations for enhancing procurement governance, including investments in user-friendly procurement systems and targeted training initiatives. These insights aim to guide supply chain leaders in leveraging digital transformation for greater cost control and operational efficiency.

Keywords: Digital Procurement, Maverick Spending, Purchasing Discipline, Procurement Automation, Cost Control.

THE ROLE OF DYNAMIC PRICING IN ENHANCING REVENUE AND OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY IN THE TRANSPORTATION SECTOR

Fahad Gull

Abstract

Dynamic pricing has become a transformative approach in the transportation sector, yet its strategic role in revenue optimization and capacity management remains underutilized in developing economies. This study investigates the effects of dynamic pricing on revenue maximization, inventory utilization, and profitability, addressing the problem of static pricing models that fail to respond to real-time market fluctuations. The objective is to evaluate user perceptions and the operational benefits of dynamic pricing mechanisms in the freight and passenger transport industry. A descriptive quantitative method was applied to survey 131 respondents through structured questionnaires, with demographic analysis covering age, gender, and education levels. The results, analyzed via SPSS, indicate that over 80% of participants perceive dynamic pricing as beneficial in adapting to demand variability and enhancing competitive pricing. Notably, 81.7% agreed it improves capacity utilization, while 77.1% affirmed its positive impact on profitability. Despite a skewed demographic (93.1% male respondents), the data strongly support the adoption of flexible pricing strategies. The study recommends broader implementation of AI-driven pricing algorithms to improve responsiveness, operational efficiency, and financial outcomes. These findings contribute to policy recommendations for digitization and strategic pricing reforms in the transportation sector.

Keywords: Dynamic Pricing, Transportation, Revenue Optimization, Capacity Utilization, Operational Efficiency.

THE STRATEGIC ROLE OF PROCUREMENT IN COST OPTIMIZATION: EVIDENCE FROM PAKISTAN'S SUPPLY CHAIN SECTOR

Abdullah Khan

Abstract

In today's volatile global business environment, cost efficiency and operational agility are critical for organizational success. This study investigates the strategic role of procurement in achieving cost optimization, emphasizing the shift from traditional transactional purchasing to a value-generating, technology-enabled function. The research focuses on dimensions such as strategic sourcing, supplier selection, risk management, digital integration, and performance measurement. A quantitative methodology was adopted, with primary data collected through structured questionnaires from 130 supply chain and procurement professionals across diverse sectors in Pakistan, including retail, logistics, and oil & gas. Using Chi-square tests, independent samples t-tests, and binary logistic regression, the analysis reveals a strong positive correlation between structured procurement practices and cost-saving outcomes. Notably, organizations implementing technology-driven solutions like e-procurement and ERP systems report enhanced stock visibility, reduced cycle times, improved supplier collaboration, and real-time analytics for better decision-making. Supplier negotiation strategies and performance metrics also emerged as key contributors to sustained cost efficiency. The findings affirm that strategic procurement is not only associated with but predictive of long-term financial performance. The study recommends investing in procurement technologies, formalizing supplier evaluation processes, and aligning procurement goals with broader organizational strategies.

Keywords: Procurement Strategy, Cost Optimization, E-Procurement, Supplier Performance.

PANEL DISCUSSION SUMMARY

Theme: *“Enhancing Performance, Agility, and Sustainability in Global Supply Chains”*

The panel discussion brought together distinguished experts from academia, industry, and technology sectors to share insights on current challenges and future strategies for supply chain optimization.

1. Balancing Cost and Resilience

The Panel emphasized that supply chains must move beyond cost minimization toward value-driven strategies. They advocated for investing in redundancy and flexibility, especially in critical supply nodes, to improve risk tolerance. The academic panelist added that the Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) model should be adopted to capture hidden costs associated with disruptions.

2. Sustainability vs. Speed

The Panel highlighted that sustainability and speed are not mutually exclusive when supported by real-time data and intelligent planning systems. He cited successful cases where automation and analytics enabled fast, low-emission logistics. The government representative added that regulatory frameworks must support green logistics through incentives for low-carbon transportation and sustainable warehousing.

3. Technology Adoption in Pakistan

All panelists acknowledged the slow pace of digital adoption in Pakistan. The academic called for stronger industry-academia collaboration to support tech training and pilot programs. The industry expert stressed the need for cost-effective, scalable solutions that suit SME environments, while the tech panelist advocated for cloud-based platforms that reduce upfront investment.

4. Skills and Talent Development

The Panel recognized the shortage of skilled professionals and outlined initiatives such as vocational training and certifications in partnership with institutions like PIFFA and DHA Suffa University. The academic echoed the need for curriculum reform and experiential learning to produce supply chain professionals ready for digital transformation.

5. Managing Geopolitical and Climate Risks

The panel concluded with a consensus that predictive analytics, scenario planning, and regional diversification are key strategies. The industry expert emphasized supplier visibility and contingency planning, while the academic encouraged integrating ESG risk assessments into core supply chain strategy.

The discussion concluded with the message that future supply chains must be resilient, digitally enabled, and driven by sustainability—not as an afterthought, but as a competitive advantage.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

It is with great pride and satisfaction that I bring the *International Conference on Innovative Strategies for Supply Chain Optimization and Efficiency (ICISSC) – 2025* to a close. Over the past two days, we have engaged in thought-provoking keynote addresses, insightful research presentations, and vibrant panel discussions that have deepened our understanding of how supply chains can be made more agile, resilient, and sustainable in an era of constant disruption.

The diversity of perspectives shared—from academia, industry, government, and technology sectors—has reaffirmed the importance of collaboration in addressing the multifaceted challenges of supply chain management. We have explored how innovation, digital transformation, and sustainability are no longer optional add-ons, but integral drivers of competitiveness in the global market.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to our keynote speakers, panelists, paper presenters, reviewers, and all participants for their valuable contributions. I also commend the tireless efforts of the organizing committee, the Business Solutions, Research & Innovation Center, the Department of Management Sciences, and our collaborating partners in making this event a success.

As we leave this conference, I encourage each of you to carry forward the ideas, networks, and inspiration gained here, transforming them into meaningful actions that strengthen our supply chains, drive economic growth, and promote environmental and social responsibility.

Thank you, and I look forward to seeing you again at future editions of ICISSC.

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